

Studies on the changes in interaction energies of salicylic acid and salicylate ion from solubility and dissociation constant measurements of salicylic acid in isopropanol + water and *t*-butanol + water mixtures at 298 K

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The solubilities and dissociation constants of salicylic acid in isopropanol (2-propanol) + water and *t*-butanol (2-methyl-2-propanol) + water mixtures have been determined. The changes in Gibbs energies of transfer of neutral salicylic acid are coupled with the changes in Gibbs energies of transfer for the dissociation processes to determine the Gibbs energy changes of transfer for salicylate ion from water to aquo-organic solvents. $\Delta G_i^\circ(\text{HSal}^-)$ is positive and passes through minima at ~34 mass% of isopropanol and ~25 and 65 mass% of *t*-butanol. The results are interpreted in terms of ion-solvent interactions and the characteristic changes in the solvent properties in these regions. In order to comprehend the ion-solvent interactions in a better way, attempts have been made to calculate the interaction energies of benzoic acid, benzoate ion, salicylic acid and salicylate ion utilizing the scaled particle theory and the data obtained from the present work and the previous works.

The Gibbs energy changes due to interaction for neutral acid, $\Delta G_{i(\text{int})}^\circ$ [water \rightarrow org. solv.] are negative and favorable but $\Delta G_{i(\text{int})}^\circ$ due to OH group is increasingly positive indicating that OH group in the *ortho*-position hinders dissolution process. The $\Delta G_{i(\text{int})}^\circ(\text{BZ}^-)$ and $\Delta G_{i(\text{int})}^\circ(\text{HSal}^-)$ are positive and $\Delta G_{i(\text{int})}^\circ(\text{BZ}^-) > \Delta G_{i(\text{int})}^\circ(\text{HSal}^-)$. The $\Delta G_{i(\text{int})}^\circ$ due to OH group in the anion is seen to be increasingly negative which can be correlated with the fact that the salicylate ion is stabilized due to hydrogen bonding leading to an increased dissociation of salicylic acid. The behavior of OH group in case of neutral acid and charged anions have been found to be exactly opposite.

Salicylic acid and its derivatives are well known for their analytic and pharmacologic activities¹⁻³. Due to hydrogen bond formation, salicylic acid may be incorporated into nucleic acid in place of neutral base leading to stabilization of complexes between drugs and receptors which would otherwise interact weakly. Salicylic acid also plays a major role in stabilizing specific folded configuration of proteins^{2,3}.

It is apparent that the introduction of OH group in the *ortho*-position brings about a marked change in its physicochemical and drug activities¹⁻³. Naturally, solute-solvent or ion-solvent interactions in salicylic acid is widely different compared to those observed for benzoic acid.

These considerations led us to determine the solubility and the dissociation constants of salicylic acid in isopropanol (2-propanol) + water and *t*-butanol (2-methyl-2-propanol) + water mixtures (0-75.8 mass% of organic solvents). The anomalous structural characteristics $\text{Pr}^1\text{OH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and *t*-butanol + H_2O mixtures⁴ may have important effect on the solubility and dissociation constants of the salicylic acid. The results are reported in this paper.

Results and Discussion

The thermodynamic dissociation constant for the reaction

is

$$K_a = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+} C_{\text{HA}^-}}{C_{\text{H}_2\text{A}}} \frac{\gamma_{\pm}^2}{\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{A}}} \\ = \frac{C_{\text{H}^+}^2}{(C_{\text{T}} - C_{\text{H}^+})} \frac{\gamma_{\pm}^2}{\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{A}}} \quad (2)$$

where C_{T} and C_{H^+} represent the total concentration and equilibrium concentration of H^+ ion in the saturated solution of salicylic acid, and γ represents activity coefficients of the respective constituents. H^+ ion concentration in the mixed solvents were determined pH-metrically. $\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{A}}$ was taken to be unity for neutral salicylic acid in the saturated solution of the acid.

The activity coefficients of the ions were calculated using the Debye-Hückel limiting equation,

$$-\log \gamma_{\pm} = AZ_+Z_- \sqrt{\mu} \quad (3)$$

with appropriate A value in each solvent,

$$A'_{\text{mixed solv.}} = 0.509 \left(\frac{78.5}{\epsilon'_{\text{mixed solv.}}} \right)^{3/2} \text{ at 298 K.}$$

The solubility and pK values of the salicylic acid in isopropanol + water and t -butanol + water mixtures determined pH-metrically are recorded in Table 1.

Table 1. Solubility and pK values of salicylic acid at 298 K determined pH-metrically

2-Propanol + water				
Mass% of Pr ⁱ OH	Solubility of salicylic acid (C_T /mol dm ⁻³)	Corrected pH	A value	pK
0.0	0.0158	3.00	0.509	3.00
8.0	0.0227	2.38	0.568	3.12
16.4	0.0417	2.33	0.650	3.32
25.1	0.191	2.20	0.751	3.79
34.3	0.493	2.11	0.899	4.08
43.9	0.893	2.03	1.101	4.18
54.0	1.245	1.98	1.417	4.28
64.6	1.480	1.94	1.934	4.48
75.8	1.650	2.04	2.697	4.82
87.9	1.938	2.25	3.633	5.34
t -Butanol + water				
Mass% of Bu ⁱ OH				
8.0	0.0225	2.40	0.605	3.15
16.4	0.0620	2.30	0.720	3.46
25.0	0.2133	2.25	0.891	3.95
34.2	0.4127	2.21	1.136	4.21
43.8	0.6760	2.15	1.530	4.39
54.0	1.024	2.09	2.192	4.59
64.5	1.753	1.98	3.442	4.91
75.8	1.910	2.15	4.996	5.42
87.6	2.325	2.70	7.969	6.48

However, pK values of weak acids determined from solubility and pH measurements may be inaccurate at higher percentages of organic solvent where the solubility values of salicylic acid are high but the dissociation of the acid is low. The meter readings in presence of large excess of undissociated acid may not be accurate. $\gamma(H_2A)$ also change appreciably from unity in case of saturated solutions of the acid and Debye-Hückel limiting law does not give correct values of γ_{\pm} in solutions of low dielectric constants. In case of t -butanol + water mixtures, phase separation (i.e. water layer and t -butanol layer) was observed between 25 and 65 mass% of t -butanol. Similar behavior was observed in case

of benzoic acid also⁵. The accuracy of pK_a values determined from solubility and pH-measurements are low except at low percentage of organic co-solvents.

In view of the limitations of the solubility method, accurate values of K_a were determined conductometrically. The method of computation suggested by Fuoss and Kraus^{6,7} was adopted. The equation connecting concentration C and equivalent conductance Λ is

$$\frac{F(Z)}{\Lambda} = \frac{1}{KA_0^2} \frac{AC\gamma_{\pm}^2}{F(Z)} + \frac{1}{A_0} \quad (4)$$

The accuracy of K_a value is dependent on A_0 . But considerable error is possible as the determination of A_0 involves large extrapolations. To avoid this, accurate A_0 values of H_2A were obtained using the relation,

$$A_0(H_2A) = A_0(HClO_4) + A_0(KHA) - A_0(KClO_4) \quad (5)$$

The A_0 values were obtained from the plots of Λ values of $HClO_4$, KHA and $KClO_4$ against $C^{1/2}$. The plots were found to be linear in water as well as in aquo-organic mixtures. The A_0 values of $HClO_4$ and $KClO_4$ in Pr^iOH were taken from our earlier communication⁸.

The values of the Onsager constants,

$$\sigma = \frac{82.4}{\eta(\epsilon T)^{1/2}} \text{ and } \theta = \frac{8.20 \times 10^3}{(\epsilon T)^{3/2}} \quad (6)$$

were calculated utilizing the η (viscosity) and ϵ (dielectric constant) values^{10,11} from the literature. The σ , θ and A_0 values previously determined were used to calculate

$$Z = \frac{(\theta A_0 + \sigma) \sqrt{AC}}{A_0^{3/2}} \quad (7)$$

and $F(Z)$ values⁷.

The values of γ_{\pm} were calculated from the limiting Debye-Hückel equation,

$$-\log \gamma_{\pm} = A \sqrt{\alpha C} \quad (8)$$

where, $\alpha = \frac{A}{A_0}$

The slopes for eqn. (4) were calculated using the method of least-squares. The values of the slopes were usually accepted only when the values of the regression coefficients were better than 0.995. The measurements were made using dilute solutions where $\gamma(H_2A)$ can be reasonably assumed to be unity and proper corrections for the activity coefficients can be made. The method is particularly suitable for the determination of K_a of weak acids in mixed and non-aqueous solvents as the method is free from assumptions.

Fuoss equation¹² was tried for several sets without substantial improvement of results. Moreover, A_0 values obtained using eqn. (4) can be considered to be more accurate than A_0 values obtained using the Fuoss equation. Niazi *et al.*¹³ reported A_0 values of benzoic and nitrobenzoic acids in EtOH + H₂O and PrOH + H₂O mixtures. They analyzed the experimental data using Lee and Wheaton¹⁴ conductance equation which is essentially the same as the Fuoss equation. The A_0 values of benzoic and substituted acids in different percentages of the binary mixtures show A_0 values reported by Niazi *et al.*¹³ to be inaccurate and inconsistent. Moreover, Niazi *et al.* found the equation not suitable beyond 50 mass% of alcohol.

The Fuoss equation was found to be suitable for electrolytes like Ph₄AsCl, NaBPh₄, NaCl in non-aqueous solvents¹⁴ but unsuitable for the determination of the first dissociation constant of H₃PO₄ in non-aqueous solvents¹⁵. Hazra *et al.*¹⁶⁻¹⁸ made extensive use of the Fuoss equation for determining A_0 and K_A (association constants) of tetraalkylammonium and related salts but not for weak acids in non-aqueous solvents.

The pK and A_0 values are recorded in Tables 2 and 3. The precision of pK_T values is ± 0.01 in water to ± 0.03 at higher percentage of binary mixtures.

The Gibbs energy of transfer for the dissociation reaction (1) from water to aquo-organic solvents can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_t^\circ(1) &= \Delta G_s^\circ(1) - \Delta G_w^\circ(1) \\ &= 2.303 RT \log \frac{m\gamma_{H^+} m\gamma_{HA^-}}{m\gamma(H_2A)} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The expression is a measure of the differences between solute-solvent interactions (of the species involved) in the two

ideal reference states with the ion-ion or solute-solute interactions eliminated¹⁷.

In the saturated solutions of salicylic acid in two solvents, the acid is in equilibrium with the same solid phase. Naturally, the Gibbs energies of the acid in two phases are also equal¹⁹. Thus

$${}_w\bar{G}_{H_2A}^\circ + RT \ln {}_w a_{H_2A}(\text{satd}) = {}_s\bar{G}_1^\circ + RT \ln {}_s a_{H_2A}(\text{satd}) \quad (10)$$

Thus, Gibbs energies of transfer of neutral salicylic acid is

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_t^\circ(H_2A) &= {}_s\bar{G}_{H_2A}^\circ - {}_w\bar{G}_{H_2A}^\circ \\ &= -2.303 RT \log \frac{{}_s a_{H_2A}(\text{satd})}{{}_w a_{H_2A}(\text{satd})} \\ &= -2.303 RT \log m\gamma_{H_2A} \\ &= -2.303 RT \log C_s/C_w \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Activity coefficients of salicylic acid should be unity in the saturated solutions of the respective solvent systems (by convention). C_s and C_w are the molar concentrations of H₂A in the solvents (s) and water (w), respectively. Appropriate corrections for the concentrations were made for the dissociation of salicylic acid in aqueous and mixed solvents.

It is not possible to compare the A_0 values in binary mixtures in absence of relevant data. However, A_0 value of salicylic acid in water comes close to A_0 value of benzoic acid⁵. The A_0 values of salicylic acid and its salts were found to decrease with increase in percentage of organic solvents and in general, A_0 (in 2-PrOH + H₂O) > A_0 (in *t*-BuOH + H₂O) having identical solvent compositions. Similar behavior was observed in case of benzoic acid also⁵.

The solubility of salicylic acid gradually increases with increase in organic solvents, i.e. with increase in hydropho-

Table 2. Equivalent conductances of electrolytes and dissociation constants of salicylic acid in 2-propanol + water mixtures at 298 K

Mass% of Pr ^o OH	1/ε 10 ²	Mole frac. of Pr ^o OH	A_0 (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)				pK	Corr. coeff. (r)
			HClO ₄	KClO ₄	C ₆ H ₄ (OH) COOK	C ₆ H ₄ (OH) COOH		
0.0	1.27	0.00	416.6	140.4	105.4	381.6	3.00	0.99
8.0	1.35	0.033	372.0	116.9	94.0	349.1	3.12	0.99
16.4	1.42	0.072	301.5	95.0	81.5	288.0	3.23	0.99
25.3	1.53	0.117	250.0	78.5	65.3	236.0	3.41	1.000
34.4	1.71	0.171	196.0	66.0	55.0	185.0	3.53	0.99
44.0	1.90	0.236	172.6	58.2	44.2	158.6	3.77	0.99
54.1	2.14	0.316	142.0	52.0	41.5	131.5	4.02	0.99
64.7	2.44	0.419	118.0	49.5	38.7	107.2	4.30	0.99
76.0	2.87	0.553	108.0	48.6	37.0	96.4	4.61	0.94
87.6	3.37	0.734	92.0	40.0	39.8	83.8	5.07	0.98

Table 3. Equivalent conductances of electrolytes and dissociation constants of salicylic acid in *t*-butanol + water mixtures at 298 K

Mass% of Bu ^l OH	1/ε 10 ²	Mole frac. of Bu ^l OH	Λ ₀ (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)					pK	Corr. coeff. (r)
			HClO ₄	KClO ₄	C ₆ H ₄ (OH) COOK	C ₆ H ₄ (OH) COOH			
8.0	1.43	0.021	321.6	110.0	82.2	293.8	3.15	1.00	
16.4	1.60	0.046	254.3	79.3	61.4	236.3	3.24	0.99	
25.0	1.85	0.075	198.9	61.2	47.3	185.0	3.63	0.00	
34.3	2.17	0.113	161.6	49.7	38.1	150.1	3.94	1.00	
43.9	2.65	0.160	125.4	40.0	28.7	114.2	4.22	1.00	
54.0	3.37	0.222	101.7	32.6	22.7	91.8	4.52	1.00	
64.6	4.55	0.307	66.5	25.6	17.0	57.9	4.82	0.99	
75.8	5.84	0.432	42.9	18.9	12.7	36.6	5.23	0.99	

bic character of the solvent mixtures, but due to hydrogen bonding the solubilities of salicylic acid in aquo-organic mixtures are always lower than those of benzoic acid. The solubilities of the acid have been found to be less in the region of 34–54 mass% of *t*-BuOH, where phase separation takes place.

The change in pK_T values, i.e. pK_T (*t*-BuOH + H₂O) > pK_T (2-PrOH + H₂O) is in the order of greater hydrophobic character (which increase the solubility of the acid) and lower relative permittivity (which decreases the ionization) of the solvent mixtures.

However, the present investigation is intended to get information regarding solute-solvent interactions and its variation with solvent composition.

Division of transfer Gibbs energy changes (ΔG_T^o) into electrostatic (ΔG_{T(elt)}^o) and non-electrostatic (ΔG_{T(nonel)}^o) contributions as done by Bates and others², i.e.

$$\Delta G_{T(i)}^o = \Delta G_{T(elt)}^o + \Delta G_{T(nonel)}^o \quad (12)$$

was avoided as ΔG_{T(nonel)}^o does not give a clear picture regarding solute-solvent basicity though the uncertainty of radii values of H⁺ ion and unsymmetrical salicylate ion and inadequacy of Born equation²¹ may be the reasons for it. But the analysis of results in terms of single ion Gibbs energy changes which give the quantitative measure of ion-solvent interactions was attempted^{5,22–24}.

We have from eqn. (1),

$$\Delta G_T^o(1) = \Delta G_T^o(H^+) + \Delta G_T^o(HA^-) - \Delta G_T^o(H_2A) \\ \text{or } \Delta G_T^o(HA^-) = \Delta G_T^o(H_2A) + \Delta G_T^o(1) - \Delta G_T^o(H^+) \quad (13)$$

ΔG_T^o(H₂A) measures the changes in solute-solvent interactions and has been calculated from solubility measurements; ΔG_T^o(H⁺) values have been taken from our previous works²⁵. The values of ΔG_T^o(HA⁻) are given in Table 5. The accuracy of ΔG_T^o(HA⁻) depends mainly on the accuracy of ΔG_T^o(H⁺) values which are generally determined using different

extrathermodynamic assumptions with their inherent limitations. ΔG_T^o(H⁺) values determined by Wells²⁶ are limited to few percentages in these solvent mixtures. The values of ΔG_T^o(H⁺) reported by Wells and our values are in qualitative agreement though Wells' method is defective and in no way gives single ion values^{27,28}. ΔG_T^o(H⁺) values for *t*-butanol + H₂O mixtures used by us (determined at 303°)²⁵ may introduce slight error but the redetermination by us at 298 K shows that the error will be not more than 0.1 kJ and can be ignored.

Thus, the errors involved in the determination of ΔG_T^o(HA⁻) are difficult to predict though an error to the extent of ±0.5 kJ may be expected. However, the experimental values show that ΔG_T^o(H⁺) and ΔG_T^o(HA⁻) values are negative and positive respectively, in agreement with the reported observations in the literature^{8,22,23,26,29}. ΔG_T^o(H⁺) shows negative maxima at ~65 mass% of Pr^lOH and 44 mass% of Bu^lOH. The corresponding minima for ΔG_T^o(HA⁻) are at 34 and ~25 mass%, respectively. These reflect the characteristic changes in the solvent properties in binary mixtures and ion-induced perturbations in these regions.

The structural properties of the aquo-alcoholic mixtures^{4,30} are dependent on (i) size of the alkyl group and related OH dilution effect. Alkyl groups are known to occupy the interstitial sites in the cluster between the icebergs and form a large number of H-bonds within the icebergs. Increase in size of alkyl group means fewer sites are available to accommodate the alkyl group and structural breakdown occurs at low x₂, the larger the alkyl groups. (ii) Decrease in the total number of molecules as we move from water to higher alcohols, though the significance of the effect is usually ignored.

It has been found that ΔH^M 4,30 (more correctly TΔS^{fi} which is slightly shifted more towards the alcohol-rich region than ΔH^M), $\bar{V}_2 - V_2^{o4,30}$ excess properties like ε_T^{E31} (excess relative permittivities of mixing) and ultrasound ab-

sorption³² maximum give valuable information regarding maximum structure formation of water molecules by alcohols. The maximum water structure formation in case of Pr^tOH + H₂O and Bu^tOH + H₂O mixtures (in terms of x_2) will be in the region,

	ΔH^M	$\bar{V}_2 - \bar{V}_2^0$	ultrasound absorption	ϵ_r^E
Pr ^t OH	0.10	$\sim < 0.1$	0.15–0.20	–0.05–0.08
Bu ^t OH	~ 0.06 –0.07	$\sim < 0.05$	~ 0.1	~ 0.02

For ions in the binary mixtures specific interactions depending on the basicity of the solvent mixtures, mutual orientation and the relative distance between the number of potential hydration sites and non-specific hydrophobic interactions play a dominant role in the structural modification of the binary mixtures^{33–35} as evident from the observed extrema in case of H⁺ and salicylate ion. The Gibbs energy changes of transfer of ions provide quantitative values of ion-solvent interactions where ion-ion interactions can be regarded to be almost eliminated. But in order to get more information and comprehend ion-solvent interactions in a better way, attempts have been made to get Gibbs energy changes due to interaction (ΔG_{int}^0) of salicylic acid, benzoic acid and related ions with solvent molecules using the scaled particle theory and the data reported earlier^{5,8,22}. The standard Gibbs energy changes associated with the dissolution of a hard sphere in a solvent can be written as^{36,37}

$$\Delta G_s^0 = \Delta G_c^0 + \Delta G_{\text{int}}^0 + RT \ln RT/V \quad (14)$$

ΔG_{int}^0 is the Gibbs energy changes of interaction between the solute molecule and surrounding solvent, V the molar volume of the solvent and ΔG_c^0 the Gibbs energy change required to create a cavity of suitable size to accommodate the solute in the solvent and is given by³⁷

$$\Delta G_c^0 = RT \{ -\ln(1-y) + 3y/(1-y)(R_1) + [3y/(1-y) + 9/2y/(1-y)^2] R_1^2 + yP/\rho kT (R_1^3) \} \quad (15)$$

$y = \pi\rho\sigma_1^3/6$ is the reduced density.

$R_1 = \sigma_2/\sigma_1$, the ratio of the hard sphere diameters of the solute (σ_2) and the solvent (σ_1), such that the radius of the cavity is $(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)/2$. P , the pressure of the system is given by

$$P/\rho kT = (1+y+y^2)/(1-y)^3 \quad (16)$$

and $\rho = N/V$, where ρ is the number average density, V the molar volume of the solvent.

Considering the mixed solvent be an assorted solvent of mean molar mass M_s , molar volume V_s , density ρ_s and diameter σ_s , we have

$$M_s = 100 [\text{mass\% of org. solv}/M_{\text{org.solv.}} + \text{mass\% of water}/18.016]^{-1} \quad (17)$$

$$V_s = M_s/\rho_s \quad (18)$$

$$\text{and } \sigma_s = 2 r_s = (6 V_s/N\pi)^{1/3} \quad (19)$$

The hard sphere diameter of the solvents have been calculated using the empirical relationship suggested by Kim³⁷,

$$\sigma_1 (\text{SPT}) = (0.9275 \pm 0.0126)\sigma_s - (0.8465 \pm 0.0084) \quad (20)$$

utilizing the data derived from eqns. (14–20) and taking $r_{\text{salicylic acid}} = r_{\text{benzoic acid}} = 2.75$ (calculated)^{5,8}, the ΔG_{int}^0 values of benzoic acid and salicylic acid in different solvents have been calculated.

The ΔG_{cav}^0 in molar scale has been obtained from the relationship,

$$\Delta G_{\text{cav}}^0 \text{molar} = \Delta G_{\text{cav}}^0 (\text{mole-fraction}) + RT \ln M_s/1000 \rho_s \quad (21)$$

In case of salicylic acid, ΔG_{int}^0 includes the specific intramolecular hydrogen bonding effects in addition to ΔG_{int}^0 due to chemical and structural variations as in benzoic acid. Thus $[\Delta G^0(\text{H}_2\text{A}) - \Delta G^0(\text{HBz})]$ can be regarded to be the contribution due to hydrogen bonding, i.e. $\Delta G_{\text{hydrogen bonding}}^0$ as all other terms are expected to cancel each other³⁸.

The ΔG_{int}^0 of benzoic acid or salicylic acid in water or in other solvents cannot be calculated in view of non-availability of relevant data of these acids in the gaseous state. Therefore, we prefer to calculate the Gibbs energy changes of transfer due to interactions, i.e. ΔG_{int}^0 from water to mixed solvents.

It is to be noted that ΔG_{cav}^0 term in the equation¹⁶ stands for one mole of solute. Theoretically, the standard Gibbs energy of solution (ΔG_s^0) by definition, is the change for transferring one mole of solid to the one molar infinite dilution standard state. Thus the cavity term is independent of the magnitude of the actual solubility, being dependent only on the radius of the hard sphere solute in a particular solvent, i.e. ΔG_c^0 is equal for molecules with equal radii, an untenable fact. Experimentally the solubility is determined by the amount of solute dissolved in a solvent at a definite temperature to make a saturated solution in which the chemical potential of the undissolved solute equals that of the dissolved solute and standard Gibbs energy change is given by $\Delta G_s^0 = -2.303 RT \log C$, where C stands for the solubility of the solute in the given solvent, i.e. solubility represents maximum amount of solute going in solution even if 1 g-mole of solute is present in the solution³⁸. Thus the Gibbs

energy changes due to cavity formation should not be the same for benzoic acid and salicylic acid due to solubility differences. Therefore, Gibbs energy changes due to cavity formation of neutral HBz or H₂A are calculated from the relation,

$$\Delta G_{(cav)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz or H}_2\text{A}) = \Delta G_{(cav)}^{\circ} C \quad (22)$$

where *C* is the solubility of HBz or H₂A (in molar units) in the appropriate solvent. The Gibbs energy of transfer of HBz or H₂A from water to mixed solvents,

$$\Delta G_1^{\circ}(\text{HBz}) = \Delta G_{(cav)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz}) + \Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz}) + \frac{RT \ln V_w / V_m}{RT \ln V_w / V_m} \quad (23)$$

and

$$\Delta G_1^{\circ}(\text{H}_2\text{A}) = \Delta G_{(cav)}^{\circ}(\text{H}_2\text{A}) + \Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}(\text{H}_2\text{A}) + \frac{RT \ln V_w / V_m}{RT \ln V_w / V_m} \quad (24)$$

can thus be utilized to calculate $\Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}$ terms. [$\Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}(\text{H}_2\text{A}) - \Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz})$] represents $\Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}(\text{OH})$, Gibbs energy change due to specific intramolecular hydrogen bonding. $\Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}(\text{H}_2\text{A})$, $\Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz})$ and $\Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}(\text{OH})$ (due to hydrogen bonding) are given in Table 4.

The free energies of transfer of anions ($X^- = \text{Bz}^-$ or HA^-) can similarly be presented as

$$\Delta G_{(x^-)}^{\circ} = \Delta G_{(cav)}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{(int)(x^-)}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{(el)}^{\circ} + \frac{RT \ln V_w / V_m}{RT \ln V_w / V_m} \quad (25)$$

where $\Delta G_{(cav)}^{\circ}$ represents the Gibbs energy change due to cavity formation of one mole of X^- ions.

The determination of $\Delta G_{(int)(X^-)}^{\circ}$ necessitates the calculation of $\Delta G_{(el)}^{\circ}$ which involves not only the energy of interactions arising from Born charging (B), but also energy of interactions like ion-dipole (i-d), ion-induced-dipole (i-i-d), ion-quadrupole (i-q) in addition to charge-transfer and other weak interactions^{37,39,40}, i.e.

$$\Delta G_{(el)}^{\circ} = \Delta G_{(el)(B)}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{(i-d)}^{\circ} + \Delta G_{(i-i-d)}^{\circ} \quad (26)$$

neglecting ion-quadrupole interaction and other weak interactions assuming spherical orientation of solvent molecules around the benzoate or salicylate ion.

The expressions for the free energy terms are²⁸⁻³⁰

$$\Delta G_{(el)(B)}^{\circ} = NZ^2e^2/2 r_i(1/\epsilon) \quad (27)$$

$$\Delta G_{(i-d)}^{\circ} = nNZ_i e\mu/(r_1 + r_s)^2 \quad (28)$$

$$\Delta G_{(i-i-d)}^{\circ} = -nN\alpha(z_i e)^2/2(r_1 + r_s)^4 \quad (29)$$

where *n*, μ , α , *r_i*, *r_s* and ϵ are solvation number (assumed to be 1 in the present case), dipole moment, polarizability, radii of the ion and the solvent, dielectric constant of the me-

Table 4. Gibbs energies (kJ mol⁻¹) of transfer of salicylic acid, benzoic acid and related terms in 2-propanol/ *t*-butanol + water mixtures at 298K

Mass% of cosolvent	$-\Delta G_{(neut)}^{\circ}$		$\Delta G_{(cav)}^{\circ}$		$-\Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}$		$\Delta G_{t, int}^{\circ}(\text{OH})$
	HBz	H ₂ Sal	HBz	H ₂ Sal	HBz	H ₂ Sal	
8.0	0.81	0.90	0.71	0.45	1.69	1.52	0.17
16.4	1.96	2.39	2.22	1.67	4.53	4.41	0.13
25.3	4.57	6.17	9.80	13.41	14.94	20.15	-5.21
34.4	7.24	8.52	32.04	30.60	40.07	39.91	0.16
44.0	8.75	9.99	58.48	54.40	68.33	65.49	2.84
54.1	9.71	10.82	84.34	73.82	95.48	86.07	9.41
64.7	9.71	11.24	102.23	85.14	113.92	98.16	15.76
76.0	10.26	11.51	122.96	90.66	136.05	104.44	31.61
<i>t</i> -Butanol + water mixtures							
8.0	0.81	0.88	0.76	0.43	1.75	1.49	0.26
16.4	2.45	3.39	5.81	3.03	8.64	6.80	1.84
25.0	5.82	6.45	17.83	12.79	24.27	19.86	4.40
34.2	7.51	8.08	36.25	25.09	44.65	34.06	10.59
43.8	8.71	9.30	58.15	40.50	68.06	51.00	17.06
54.0	9.80	10.33	88.11	59.76	99.47	71.65	27.74
64.5	10.50	11.66	112.80	98.81	125.29	112.46	12.83
75.8	10.91	11.88	126.68	102.37	140.10	116.76	23.34

$$\Delta G_{(cav)}^{\circ} = [\Delta G_{s(cav)}^{\circ} C_s - \Delta G_{w(cav)}^{\circ} C_w]$$

$$\Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ} = [\Delta G_{(neut)}^{\circ} - \Delta G_{(cav)}^{\circ} - RT \ln V_w / V_m]$$

$$\Delta G_{t, int}^{\circ}(\text{OH}) = \Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}(\text{H}_2\text{Sal}) - \Delta G_{(int)}^{\circ}(\text{HBz})$$

It is to be noted that the scaled particle theory as utilized in the paper has limitations. However, no method is perfect and can predict quantitatively the salient features in solu-

Table 6.

Cell const. = 0.758 cm⁻¹, Temp. = 298 K
Solvent : water

Conc. of salicylic acid × 10 ³ M	10 ² AC	10 ⁴ 1/A	10 ⁴ [F(Z)/A]	10 ² [ACf _± ² /F(Z)]
0.578	15.50	37.29	36.99	14.90
1.156	26.12	44.26	43.77	24.83
1.734	34.49	50.28	49.69	32.51
2.312	41.16	56.17	55.46	38.59
2.890	48.36	59.76	58.93	45.09

Solvent : 25.1 mass% of PrⁱOH

0.578	5.53	104.40	103.59	52.70
1.156	8.87	130.30	129.03	83.34
1.734	11.54	150.16	148.51	107.51
2.312	13.86	166.82	164.80	128.15
2.890	15.84	182.39	180.03	145.71

Solvent : 54.0 mass% of PrⁱOH

0.578	1.24	467.24	462.42	11.59
1.156	1.89	609.54	601.73	17.51
1.734	2.43	712.20	701.94	22.23
2.312	2.92	791.83	779.31	26.44
2.890	3.39	851.61	837.04	30.49

Table 7.

Cell const. = 0.758 cm⁻¹, Temp. = 298.15 K
Solvent : 16.4 mass% of BuⁱOH

Conc. of salicylic acid × 10 ³ M	10 ³ AC	10 ³ 1/A	10 ³ [F(Z)/A]	10 ² [ACf _± ² /F(Z)]
0.578	81.48	7.09	7.04	77.22
1.156	133.49	8.64	8.55	124.83
1.734	177.07	9.79	9.68	163.46
2.312	213.22	10.84	10.70	195.44
2.890	244.30	11.83	11.66	222.54

Solvent : 43.8 mass% of BuⁱOH

0.578	16.30	35.47	35.11	15.13
1.156	24.98	46.28	45.70	22.77
1.734	32.05	54.09	53.32	28.87
2.312	38.35	60.28	59.34	34.21
2.890	43.43	66.54	65.43	38.45

Solvent : 54.0 mass% of BuⁱOH

0.578	8.37	69.07	68.28	7.68
1.156	13.09	88.30	87.05	11.76
1.734	16.98	102.08	100.41	15.03
2.312	20.42	113.22	111.20	17.86
2.890	23.91	120.88	118.55	20.68

Table 8. Equivalent conductances of HClO₄ in *t*-butanol + water mixtures at 298.15 K

Solvent : 8.0 mass% of BuⁱOH

Concn. of HClO ₄ 10 ³ c (mol dm ⁻³)	A S cm ² mol ⁻¹	10 ² √C	A ⁰ S cm ² mol ⁻¹
1.0	316.35	3.16	
2.0	314.10	4.47	
2.5	313.31	5.00	321.60
4.0	311.0	6.32	
5.0	295.1	7.07	

Solvent : 34.3 mass% of BuⁱOH

1.0	157.50	3.16	
2.0	155.72	4.47	
2.5	155.12	5.00	161.60
4.0	133.46	6.32	
5.0	152.36	7.07	
10.0	148.60	10.00	

Solvent : 75.8 mass% of BuⁱOH

1.0	39.30	3.16	
2.0	37.86	4.47	
2.5	37.17	5.00	42.85
4.0	35.66	6.32	
5.0	34.51	7.07	

Table 9. Equivalent conductances of KClO₄ in *t*-butanol + water mixtures at 298 K

Solvent : 8.0 wt% of BuⁱOH

Concn. of C ₆ H ₅ COOK 10 ³ c (mol dm ⁻³)	A S cm ² mol ⁻¹	10 ² √C	A ⁰ S cm ² mol ⁻¹
1.0	105.6	3.16	
2.0	103.37	4.47	
2.5	102.52	5.00	110.00
4.0	100.27	6.32	
5.0	99.0	7.07	
10.0	94.1	10.00	

Solvent : 34.3 wt % of BuⁱOH

1.0	47.68	3.16	
2.0	46.80	4.47	
2.5	46.56	5.00	49.65
4.0	45.67	6.32	
5.0	45.27	7.07	
10.00	43.40	10.00	

Solvent : 54.0 wt % of BuⁱOH

1.0	30.41	3.16	
2.0	29.49	4.47	
2.5	29.06	5.00	32.57
4.0	28.18	6.32	
5.0	27.61	7.07	

tions. Therefore, attempts should be made to refine the calculations and derive maximum useful information on the various aspects of solution chemistry.

Experimental

2-Propanol or isopropanol (A.R., B.D.H.) was distilled and the middle fraction was utilized within 24 h ($\eta_D^{298} = 1.3758$, $d = 0.7816$). *t*-Butanol (A.R., SDS) was treated with lime, kept overnight and distilled. The distillate was frozen below 293 K and the supernatant liquid was rejected. The crystallized mass was melted and finally distilled. The middle fraction ($\eta_D = 1.3847$, $d = 0.7808$) was utilized for the preparation of the solution. Conductivity water (sp. cond. = 1.1×10^{-6} S cm⁻¹) was used for the preparation of solutions. The binary mixtures were prepared by mixing known volumes of the appropriate solvents. The densities of the binary mixtures were determined using a calibrated pycnometer. The dielectric constants of the binary mixtures were taken from the literature^{10,11}.

Salicylic acid (G.R., E. Merck) was used without further purification. It was, however, heated to 383 K in an air-oven for 1 h and kept in a vacuum desiccator. Perchloric acid (G.R., E. Merck) was estimated in the usual way. Caustic soda, caustic potash, succinic acid and potassium hydrogenphthalate (G.R., E. Merck) were used. Potassium hydrogen salicylate was prepared by exact neutralization of salicylic acid with one equivalent of KOH solution. KClO₄ (Puriss, Fluka) was crystallized from water, dried and kept in a desiccator.

For the determination of solubility of salicylic acid, the saturated solution of the acid was prepared at about 2° above the experimental temperature, i.e. 298 K. The clear solution, taken in a Campbell solubility⁴² apparatus was allowed to equilibrate in a thermostat maintained at 298 ± 0.02 K for 6 h^{5,43,44}. After equilibrium, the apparatus was inverted in the thermostat. A definite amount of the filtered solution was utilized. The solubilities of salicylic acid in aquo-organic mixtures were determined titrimetrically with standardized NaOH solution using phenolphthalein as indicator. But due to the presence of OH group in salicylic acid, the titrimetric method may not be free from error. The solubility of salicylic acid was, therefore, determined spectrophotometrically from the absorptivity values of the appropriately diluted solution at the isosbestic point (300 nm) of the absorption curves of salicylic acid and sodium hydrogen salicylate and molar absorptivity values of the acid previously determined at the same wavelength.

The solubility values using the two methods differed (within 1%) and the spectrophotometric values (Table 1)

were preferred. The method could not be used in the region 25–65 mass% of *t*-butanol + water mixtures where phase separation occurred in excess of salicylic acid similar to those observed in case of benzoic acid⁵. To determine the solubility of salicylic acid in this region, a definite volume of mixed solvent of known composition was taken and the salicylic acid was added in small amounts with shaking until turbidity appeared and then disappeared after addition of 2–3 drops of binary mixture. Repeated trials were made to have reproducible results.

The dissociation constant of salicylic acid was determined by coupling the solubility and the pH value of the saturated solution of the acid. The pH was measured using a Systronics pH-meter having a reproducibility of 0.01 pH unit. In absence of suitable buffers in binary mixtures, glass electrodes could not be standardized in the usual way. Standardization of the pH-meter and determination of H⁺ concentration were made following the procedure suggested by Van Uitert and Hass and used extensively by other^{45–50}. The reproducibility and accuracy of the determination were checked in the way described before^{48–50}. However, pH-meter readings containing excess of salicylic acid in saturated solutions in aquo-binary mixtures show considerable error and the results are erroneous. For the conductometric determination of salicylic acid, the conductances of salicylic acid at different concentrations (2.0×10^{-3} to 5.0×10^{-4} M) and those for HClO₄, KClO₄ and potassium hydrogen salicylate (5.0×10^{-4} to 5.0×10^{-2} M) in the appropriate binary mixtures were measured with a Leeds-Northrup 4959 conductivity bridge with a sensitivity of $\pm 0.1\%$. A 50–60 or 1000 cycle signal was employed depending on the conditions of the experiments. A dip-type Philips conductance cell was used. The value of the cell constant (0.758 cm⁻¹) was verified⁵¹. The measurements were made at 298 ± 0.02 K. Some representative data are presented in additional Tables 6–9.

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